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THE IMPACT OF INTERNET INTEGRATION TO DEVELOP READING ABILITY OF STRUGGLING READERS: AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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Abstract:

Reading is the basic fundamental skills in teaching-learning process, thus every learner must know how to read . However there were some students who where known as “struggling readers,” the ones who are known to be in frustration stage as classified by Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI).

Therefore , it is conducted to investigate the effects of internet integration on the development of reading abilities among struggling readers, specifically focusing on silent and oral reading. Twenty-seven (27) Grade 5 struggling readers from Compostela Central Elementary School SPED Center participated. Pretests and posttests were conducted to measure reading speed and comprehension scores. Results showed significant improvements in both silent and oral reading abilities post-intervention. The findings suggest that ICT integration positively impacts reading proficiency among struggling readers, highlighting its potential as a valuable tool in education.

Keywords: struggling readers, reading ability, ICT integration, Quasi-experimental study

1. Introduction

Reading is a fundamental skill a student must possess which offers a life-long opportunity of success in any field that a student would have. It is an important skill to develop because it is necessary for an individual to function in the community where he/she belongs. It is basically needed for communication and to understand what the other individual would like to communicate and to facilitate to learn reading, the technology in our midst can facilitate how to read and to comprehend what has been read.

According to Pardede (2019), technology in the sector of education has overwhelmed the teaching and learning process with digital tools. Internet connection can provide any kind of information people want to know, and this has changed the habit of students in gathering of data instead of visiting the library and read printed books, students tend to access digital texts through the internet. The internet is one of the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) which is a good means to develop the reading ability of the students since they are already exposed to it. With the growing amount of digital information available, students are more particular spending time reading electronic materials. However, only few studies focusing on the effects of the use of internet to develop reading ability of the students who are specifically struggling.

In the Philippines, a study conducted by Honey Lyn P. Valentos and Ronald S. Decano found that print and non-print materials were not the only resources that helped frustrated learners with their self-learning modules during the pandemic. Digital learning materials, including audio-visual content, also played a significant role.

A study as conducted in Indonesia by Nurhana (2014) that aimed to improve the reading skills of 8th grade students of SMP Raden Fatah Cimanggu, Cilacap by using Interactive Multimedia. The subjects of the study were the VIII E students of SMP Raden Fatah Cimanggu, Cilacap in the academic year of 2013/2014. The data from the observation and interview were analyzed qualitatively and the scores were analyzed quantitatively. The finding of this study is that the using of the Interactive Multimedia could improve the students' reading skills at SMP Raden Fatah Cimanggu, Cilacap. The results of the research show that there is improvement of the students' reading skills through the use of Interactive Multimedia. The students made a good improvement in some aspects of reading skills, such grammatical words classes, system, particular meaning, and task achievement. They were more confident to reading aloud. They actively participated during the teaching and learning process.

In Compostela Central Elementary School where the researcher is teaching, it was observed that many classrooms are already equipped with smart televisions and internet connections. Amidst this technology, there are still many students who are struggling how to read. This is the reason why the researcher would like to delve into this study to determine whether the integration of this internet help the struggling reader to read. Research shows that 80% of the learner's learning can be achieved visually, thus in using chalkboard the teacher can only present pictures by posting them whereas by the use of multimedia he can share video lessons which are more interesting than the former.

Literature Review

The succeeding paragraphs present the related literatures of this study. Different studies regarding whether the class using internet gains a higher educational attainment compared to those students adapting the traditional way of teaching.

Reading. It is very vital for the overall improvement of a human being. According to Chettri and Rout (2013), reading affords experience through which an individual may enlarge his horizons of knowledge, identify, spread and increase his awareness and advances a deeper understanding of himself, of other people and of the world. In the context of education, a large amount of reading is essential because all learning activities involve reading skills and the success of students' study also depends on the greater part in their ability to read. Bashir and Mattoo (2012) emphasized that both reading and academic success are consistent and dependent relative to each other.

Additionally, Palani (2012) stated that reading is interconnected with the total educational development and educational achievement needs successful reading. Krashen's (2004) study⁴ revealed that people with good reading habits tend to score better on all kinds of tests.

In the EFL context, reading is essentially the most important skill every learner should master. Pardede (2019) identified three reasons why reading is crucial for EFL learners. First, EFL learners lack inputs from their daily interactions because English is not the primary language of the society where they study it. To overcome the input limitation, reading is the best solution. Secondly, reading significantly contributes to one's personal and intellectual development, further studies, job success, and career development, and the capability to meet changes. Third, reading skills enhance a learner's mastery of other areas of language teaching because it offers the learners with various good sentence structures so many times that they become accustomed to them.

Reading also develops EFL learners' vocabulary by letting them get the most frequently used and useful words and learned them in context. It also improves writing skills for it enables the learners to figure out how to express ideas through words, how to use punctuation correctly, and so on⁵. Reading is even the basis of instruction in all aspects of language learning. .

Realizing the importance of reading, its development has been regarded as the first priority in EFL and printed texts have long played a great role in EFL classrooms. However, the increasing use of digital text in EFL learning and teaching due to the influx of digital tools has caused a fundamental change in the ways students read today (Pardede, 2019). Digital texts have two main types: the one accessed from the internet and those kept in screen reading tools, computers or hand handled devices. Both are electronically generated and multimodal (blending texts with audio, video, image, and hypertext). Such features make them more interactive than a printed text and bid the reader to explore in a nonlinear way. Hypertext, in particular, makes a digital text interconnected with many other texts which offer the readers various directional choices fitting to their interest. So, a single text can provide different access routes and, therefore, different options of reading. In this context, the hyper-textual nature promotes a flexible pattern of discovery that fosters readers' greater cognitive effort for they must construct information frameworks based on the nature of the paths chosen (Spires & Estes, 2002).

Digital reading has both advantages and disadvantages for students. On the one hand, it makes reading and information accessibility easier and more enjoyable. On the other hand, it poses a threat to reading culture. One of the advantages of internet-based reading is that reading is now not focused on one place, silent and starts to read. Students can now read anywhere and anytime as long as they feel enjoy and comfortable. Another advantage is that using the internet-connected with media technology (computer) can generate a big motivation and enthusiasm to read. This fact is evidence that students have a favorable perception of the use of the internet in learning reading comprehension subjects. Sudiran (2015) listed several benefits of the internet-based-reading: (1) motivating students; (2) improving the quality of learning processes; (3) reducing the 64 Journal of English Teaching, Volume 6 (1), February 2020 Bana DOI: 10.33541/jet.v6i1.46 misunderstanding among students; (4) increasing the students' curiosity; and (5) increasing the students' competitiveness to achieve their goals". Currently, most people believe that the success of graduates of each college or school is depending on how they learn to apply or use the internet as a source for gathering information. As a means of increasing knowledge, the internet plays a key role in learning reading comprehension because it helps students acquired much information

from which their achievement has developed. The use of the internet for reading English makes students more capable and creative in learning. 6

However, various previous studies tended to suggest that printed or paper-based reading was superior to digital or screen-based reading tasks in terms of speed, accuracy, and comprehension. Mayes et al. (2001) also found computer-based reading significantly slower. However, a more recent study (Solak, 2014) revealed that reading speed on a screen reading was nearly 12% faster than paper-based reading.

In terms of comprehension, various studies (Macedo-Rouet et al., 2003; Mangen et al. 2013; Solak, 2014) showed paper-based reading supremacy, while others (Abanomey, 2013; Aydemir et al. 2013; Huang, 2014; Taj et al. 2017) found that digital reading outperformed paper-based reading for comprehension. These contradictory results of studies investigating the effect of paper-based reading versus screen-based reading to reading speed, accuracy, and comprehension, according to Pardede (2017) is due to two factors. First, the varieties of the study designs, including the heterogeneity of the subjects' age-group and sample size inadequacy, varied settings, diverse independent and dependent variables, unclear measures validity and reliability, and inappropriate mastery or even absence of digital reading strategies among the participants. Second, the various advancement levels of the technology employed in the study.

Numerous recent studies (Jeong, 2012; Lim & Hew, 2014) examining students' and teachers' perceptions of digital reading focus on the use of e-books commonly revealed that more than 50% of users who had used e-books were satisfied with their experience of using them. Pardede (2019) found that pre-service English teachers perceived digital modules use in blended learning positively. But they expected the modules to be written in 'easier' language and accompanied by relevant videos. Jeong (2012) indicated that Korean students approved e-books. The students also admitted the current e-book's usefulness. Lim and Hew (2014) found that students generally held positive attitudes toward e-book. Some other studies focused on comparing the preference for digital texts with their counterparts.

Abdullah and Gibb (2008) revealed that users still prefer reading paper books for various reasons: preference of the feel for real books, disinclination to read on the screen, or difficulty to purchase the equipment. However, Eden and Eshet-Alkalai's (2013) study showed no significant differences in readers' average scores on the two formats, but participants reading the digital format finished their assignments faster.

Information and Communication Technology. It is one of the foremost technologies among the emerging technologies that play an important role in every sphere of human endeavor. It has witnessed a massive transformation over the years which makes teaching and learning easier and more enjoyable, and has changed the ways people live, learn, work, and play. Consequently, the internet has been a vital tool to the present information society, and a world without the internet is unimaginable (Adelakun et al., 2020). This study aims to investigate the impact of information and communication technology on students' learning engagement and academic performance. According to UNESCO, Information and communication technology (ICT) is defined as a technological and engineering discipline that uses scientific and management techniques in information handling (Ratheeswari, 2018). Hence, it uses different technologies to capture, communicate, collect, analyse, store and distribute the information needed to perform a specific task faster (Bobillier Chaumon et al., 2014; Pedagoo, 2020).

It is imperative to note that the outbreak of the Covid-19 Pandemic forced several higher institutions of learning in developing countries to adopt digital technology for the learning process (Adelakun & Omolola, 2020).

Moreover, Adelakun et al., (2022) studied the benefits, challenges and prospects of Electronic Learning System using two research processes administered to students and lecturers, and the findings of their study show that information technology will improve performance and lead to greater productivity when standard IT infrastructure is installed. Hence, all education curricula should be incorporated with appropriate digital technology to meet the present and future challenges of globalization and the knowledge economy.

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Thierer (2000) pointed out that the role of technology in teaching and learning is rapidly becoming one of the most important and widely discussed issues in contemporary education policy. Its importance has been recognized by educational institutions worldwide (Watson, 2001). As one of the most important needs for the well-being of individuals and communities at large, education in union with ICT prepares one to take on present day tasks and challenges even better. It is opined that ICTs are the building blocks for today's society, (UNESCO, 2002) as they are seen to have changed and still changing many aspects of people's ways of life. When one dives into fields as medicine, tourism, business, law, travel, engineering, architecture and banking, there is a great deal of appreciation on the influence of ICT especially in the past two to three decades. (Collis, 2002) Times have truly changed; ICT is indispensable in the contemporary world. Therefore, culture and society have to be adjusted to meet the challenges of the information age. If one looks at education sector, there seems to be little impact of ICT utilization and far less change, than other fields have experienced. However, education is a powerful instrument of social, political, and economic progress, without which neither an individual nor a society can attain professional growth (Collis, 2002).

Technology has been redefined in the 21st century to encompass a broad spectrum of sectors. Nowadays, many countries consider technology to be a knowledge transfer highway such that its integration has gone through innovations and transformed our societies to change people's perception, work and lifestyle (Grabe, 2007). As a result, schools and other educational foundations which are supposed to prepare students to live in "a knowledge society" need to consider ICT integration in their curriculum (Ghavifekr, Afshari, & Amla, 2012). Those institutions that train their students in yesterday's skills and outdated technologies are not meeting the needs of tomorrow's world. Such children will not fit into tomorrow's professional requirements. Integrating technology into schools takes time; it is an ongoing and continuous process. (Young, 2003) Once it is established, there is a dynamic and proactive learning environment. (Hatlevik & Arnseth, 2012)

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In order to highlight the importance of ICTs in the future of education, an International Conference on ICT in Education in Qingdao, China was organised by UNESCO which brought together approximately 65 Ministers of Education, resulting in the Qingdao Declaration. This new international declaration put countries in a commitment to integrating ICT into their education systems amongst other objectives (UNESCO, 2015b). It is noteworthy that ICT is evolving at an increasingly rapid pace. For example new platforms such as mobile technologies, cloud computing, social media, as well as the hardware used, are transforming education and schools so quickly.

Access to internet service is crucial in order that various ICTs are used to their potential. Nevertheless, Ministries of education often have little or no control over school Internet connectivity as this depends to a great extent on the level of development of the national telecommunications infrastructure and access to a reliable power supply (World Bank, 2010). Internet availability varies in the different regions; it remains a significant challenge in South and West Asia and sub-Saharan Africa. Meanwhile, high income countries in the Pacific, East Asia and the Caribbean have it readily available. (Martinez et al., 2009) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS), 2012)

Technology's Influence on Student Comprehension was a study conducted by Clar (2015) in Abstract This research question asked how can technology influence students' comprehension? Research was conducted in a first grade classroom. The data was collected by a student focus group, student work samples, rubrics, and teacher field notes. Findings revealed that students are engaged while using technology; however they are just as engaged when involved in a traditional read aloud. As for reading comprehension students' showed an increase in achievement when using the smart board as the primary source of instruction. Overall, data shows that teachers should implement technology in the classroom to promote student participation as well as increased achievement (Clark, 2015).
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According to the World Bank statistics, internet was present in a negligible proportion (near 50%) of schools in Guinea and Madagascar in 2013 and in Liberia in 2014. Africa is on the rise in the technological sphere especially sub-Saharan countries that are still developing. That said, her experience with technology integration is lagging behind first world countries. A combination of education and ICT can be a powerful driver for growth on the African continent (Shana & Marlene, 2015). In all the different aspects of ICT in relation to education, South Africa boasts decades of accumulated experience from its wide range of projects and programs. The scale of all these interventions to date has led to at least 22 percent computer penetration in all public schools. (Iseac, 2007))

Information and communication technology can make the school more efficient and productive, as it organizes a variety of tools to enhance and facilitate teachers' professional activities. (Yusuf & Onasanya, 2004)) were of the opinion that ICT is a means for school to communicate with one another through e-mail, mailing list, chat room and other facilities. It provides quicker and easier access to more extensive and current information. ICT can also be used to do complex tasks as it provides researchers with a steady avenue for the dissemination of research reports and findings. Experts in the fields of education have agreed that, if ICT is properly used, it holds great promise to improve teaching and learning in addition to shaping work-force opportunities.

The field of education has been affected by ICTs, which have undoubtedly affected teaching and research. The many benefits of ICT in education as proven in a variety of research have facilitated its integration in developed countries. In the Nigerian context, there has been some level of ICT integration in secondary schools (Yusuf, Maina, & Dare, 2013).
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The integration of computers into secondary schools was traced back to 1988 when the Nigerian government enacted a policy on computer education. The Federal Government of Nigeria in the National Policy on Education (2007) recognizes the prominent role of ICTs in the modern world. In a bid to actualize the integration of ICT in schools, the document stated that the government will provide basic infrastructure and training at the primary school. At the junior secondary school,

computer education is made a pre-vocational elective and is a vocational elective at the senior secondary school (Yusuf, Maina, & Dare, 2013).

Information and communication technology (ICT) has become so influential in current society that it infiltrates every aspect of life. (Thierer, 2000) pointed out that the role of technology in teaching and learning is rapidly becoming one of the most important and widely discussed issues in contemporary education policy. Its importance has been recognized by educational institutions worldwide (Watson, 2001). As one of the most important needs for the well-being of individuals and communities at large, education in union with ICT prepares one to take on present day tasks and challenges even better. It is opined that ICTs are the building blocks for today's society, (UNESCO, 2002) as they are seen to have changed and still changing many aspects of people's ways of life. When one dives into fields as medicine, tourism, business, law, travel, engineering, architecture and banking, there is a great deal of appreciation on the influence of ICT especially in the past two to three decades. Times have truly changed; ICT is indispensable in the contemporary world. Therefore, culture and society have to be adjusted to meet the challenges of the information age. If one looks at education sector, there seems to be little impact of ICT utilization and far less change, than other fields have experienced. However, education is a powerful instrument of social, political, and economic progress, without which neither an individual nor a society can attain professional growth. (Collis, 2002).

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Role of ICT in Education. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been credited for its creativity in the teaching and learning process as it breaches the gap between teacher-centered and student-centered teaching methods (Asenso-Okyere & Mekonnen, 2012). ICT is able to augment the tools and environment for learning because it allows materials to be presented in multiple media, motivates and engages students in the learning process, fosters inquiry and exploration, and provides access to world-wide information resources (Haddad, 2003). Nevertheless, researches in their findings have been inconclusive on the expectations regarding the value of ICT (Trucano, 2005).

As mentioned above, the teacher-centered and student-centered teaching methods must be addressed equally. In that respect, ICT can be relevant in the teachers' professional development, to make them guides to sources of knowledge. In recent years, teachers have to acquaint themselves with ICTs as a support system, which provides a broad platform for easily accessible knowledge. (Gallimore & Stigler, 2013) Also, they must be life-long learners to keep abreast of new knowledge, pedagogical ideas and technology (World Bank, 2003). Through the digital libraries, virtual institutions, and other Internet resources teachers can easily have access to relevant and current resources in their areas. It is worth noting that the quality of students' learning is enhanced through their access to the needed content through ICT facilities (especially, the Internet). ICT Improves learning when there is an increase the information available to learners, thereby engendering collaborative learning (World Bank, 2003).

Academic Performance. Intelligence is also measured in terms of academic achievement. While there is little doubt about the crucial role such accomplishments play in student life and subsequently (Kell, Lubinski, & Benbow, Citation2013), it was long believed to be the most significant result of formal educational experiences.

Information Communication Technology (ICT). Information and communication technology (ICT) is employed extensively in the field of education today. ICT comprises computers, the Internet, and electronic delivery systems including radios, televisions, and projectors among others. According to Kent and Facer (2004), the school setting is crucial for kids to engage in a wide variety of computer-related activities, while the home setting is a supplementary location for regular participation in a smaller range of computer-related activities. ICT is increasingly being used successfully in teaching, learning, and assessment.

ICT is seen as a potent tool for changing and reforming education. A number of earlier research have demonstrated that effective ICT use can improve educational quality and link classroom instruction to real-world contexts (Lowther, et al. 2008; Weert and Tatnall 2005). According to Weert and Tatnall (2005), learning is a continuous, lifelong process in which students deviate from conventional methods and alter their expectations by actively seeking knowledge. They will need to be ready and willing to seek out new information sources as time goes on. For these kids, ICT proficiency will be a critical requirement. The flipped classroom approach is being used by certain teachers with the aid of technology. As a result, the kids are able to engage in class and learn the material at home.

In another study, Klopfer, et al. (2009) discussed how students are growing up and are completely normalized by digital technologies. The study explained that "many students in this group are using new media and technologies to create new things in new ways, learn new things in new ways, and communicate in new ways with new people-behaviors that have become hardwired in their ways of thinking and operating in the world".

ICT (internet). A research by Chien, Wu and Hsu (2014) has shown that students in school are having high expectation on ICT integration in classroom as the new generation are born and grown with technologies and could be define as the digital – native phenomenon. The younger the students, the higher their expectation are on ICT integration in classroom. It also proved that the integration of ICT is mostly dependent on the personal factors which define as self-perceptions.

The integration of ICT in classroom is getting more important as it help student in enhancing their collaborative learning skills as well as developing transversal skills that stimulates social skills, problem solving, self-reliance, responsibility and the capacity for reflection and initiative. All these elements are core values that students need to achieve in an active teaching and learning environment (Ghavifekr et al., 2014). Similarly, in Malaysia the government has implemented the integration of ICT in learning and teaching process in early 1970's. This is due to the importance of technology literate which produce critical thinking workforce to face and involve the country in the global economy (Hamidi, Meshkat, Rezaee, & Jafari, 2011). Accordingly, many schools were upgraded with computer's lab, the internet connection, smart white boards, LCD and other ICT tools and equipment. Despite all these, the problem faced was the teachers' skill and aptitude, technical support and stability of the system in order to implement the policy successfully. However, the government is still improving and upgrading the systems to be fully utilizing by ICT.

ICT can bring real life issues into classrooms in a way that was not possible before in a traditional classroom setting. The flexible nature of ICT and the internet especially provide pupils (and others) with the opportunities for research, interaction, cooperation and collaboration (Cole, 2000). Utilizing moving and still images, conducting life histories, carrying out social research through ICT might make social studies meaningful and enjoyable which is otherwise might be considered a dull subject by some pupils (Dawson et al., 2000; Acun, 2012).

ICT and pupils achievement. The hype about ICT has also implications about its effect on pupils' achievement and engagement in learning activities. The implications of it are promising considering the infusion of ICT into every aspect of human life. Human experience as we know it has been changing in interaction, entertainment, commerce, health and education due to ICT. This change is immense and irreversible. Teachers have no or very little power on the infusion of ICT in pupils' lives. The positive impact of ICT on pupils' achievement is what educators would want to happen in a situation that is going to happen anyway. What they need is to adopt themselves and their practice to make the best out of ICT. When teachers are digitally literate and trained to use ICT, these approaches can lead to higher order thinking skills, provide creative and individualized options for students to express their understandings, and leave students better prepared to deal with on-going technological change in society and the workplace (Efe, 2011).

3. Material and Methods

The study was a quasi-experimental research using one-group pretest-posttest design. Quasi-experimental research is similar to experimental research in that there is manipulation of an independent variable. It differs from experimental research because either there is no control group, no random selection, no random assignment, and/or no active manipulation (Abraham & MacDonald, 2011). Furthermore, this study used the quasi-experiment known as the one-group pretest-posttest design in which the same dependent variable is measured in one group of the subjects. This quasi-experimental research is not true experimental research. Although the

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independent variable is manipulated, the subjects are not randomly assigned to conditions or order of conditions.

This study aimed to determine the effects of internet integration to develop the reading ability of struggling readers in terms of reading speed both silent and oral ; in terms of comprehension score both silent and oral.

The subjects of the study were the 27 struggling readers from the Grade 5 learners as identified by their advisers based on the Phil-Iri tool. These students were officially enrolled at Compostela Central Elementary School SPED-Center for school year 2022-2023. The subjects were identified and categorized as struggling readers.

The researcher used the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) GST to determine the reading proficiency level of the pupils. According to Phil-IRI Manual (2018), the Phil-IRI Group Screening Test (GST) can tell teachers whether students were reading at, above, or below their grade levels. After the assessment of the GST result, the researcher divided the instrument into three parts: Part 1 dealt with word recognition wherein pupils at risk were tested through identifying their reading miscues in terms of mispronunciation, omission, repetition, insertion, and substitution following this formula below:

$$\text{Word Recognition} = \frac{\text{Number of words} - \text{Number of major miscues}}{\text{Number of words in the passage}} \times 100$$

Part 2, the questionnaire dealt with identifying the reading level of the pupils as independent, instructional, and frustration considering the criteria of Phil-IRI Reading level below:

	Word Recognition	-	Comprehension Score (in%)	-	
Independent	97-100%	-	80-100%	-	
Instructional	90-100%	-	59-79%	-	
Frustration	89%-below	-	58%-below	-	

To formally start this research, an endorsement letter from the Graduate School of the Assumption college of Nabunturan was submitted to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS), Division of Davao de Oro. After which another letter was prepared addressing it SDS to ask permission for the conduct of the study. Another written request was given to the principal of Compostela Central Elementary School SPED Center asking permission to allow the researcher to conduct the study. The study underwent a research ethical evaluation by the ethics committee (REC). Likewise, the researcher also asked the cooperation of the parents during the conduct of the intervention whereby ICT integration was used. Upon receiving the confirmation from the authorities, the researcher prepared the pretest that was used before the intervention. The same material was also used during the posttest.

To start the study, pre-test was administered to the identified struggling readers. After a month of teaching Using ICT (Internet) in teaching, a post-test will be administered. The results between the pre-test and posttest were treated as students' mean gain scores. The mean gain scores were the basis in testing the significant difference between the performance of the students in pretest and posttest.

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The researcher gathered all data and assess the responses of the pupils. The recorded data was analyzed using the instrument to classify the pupils according to independent, instructional, and frustration and above all to determine if the pupils have improve on their reading ability level and if there was a difference on their performance after the intervention using ICT (Internet) integration.

The data obtained were tallied and tabulated. The statistical tools used to ensure the accuracy in the analyses and interpretations of the findings are the following:

Mean used to measure the central tendency between the pretest and posttest mean scores in the reading test of pupils.

Paired T-Test was used in computing the significant difference of two groups of sample.

4. Results and Discussion

Reading Ability of the Subjects in Silent and Oral Reading During the Pre-test

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics for Pretest in Oral Reading and Silent Reading				
	Pre -test Silent Reading Speed	Pre-test Oral Reading Speed	Pre-test Silent Reading Comprehension Score	Pre-test Oral Reading Comprehension Score
Valid	27	27	27	27
Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean	15.622	10.063	0.111	0.111
Std. Deviation	2.105	3.096	0.424	0.424
Minimum	13.800	0.000	0.000	0.000
Maximum	23.400	2.000	2.000	2.000

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics for pretest in oral reading and silent reading abilities of subjects in terms of speed and comprehension score. The mean of speed recorded during the pretest for silent reading is 15.6 words per minute, while the mean score achieved during the same pretest for silent reading stands at 0.11. The class proficiency for this is calculated at 1.6%. The results suggest that the class proficiency in terms of reading is categorized as very low.

On the same table also, the comprehension score in pre-test both oral and silent is of same value, 0.11 percent.

Level of Reading Abilities of the Subjects in Silent and Oral Reading During the Post-test

Table 2

Reading Abilities of the Subjects in Silent and Oral Reading During the Post-test

	Post -test Silent Reading Speed	Post-test Oral Reading Speed	Post-test Silent Reading Comprehension Score	Post-test Oral Reading Comprehension Score
Valid	27	27	27	27
Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean	35.481	39.237	1.593	1.296
Std. Deviation	11.628	13.457	1.693	1.540
Minimum	20.500	14.800	0.000	0.000
Maximum	63.300	62.300	6.000	6.000

Table 2 presents the reading ability of the subjects in silent and oral reading during the post-test. It reveals that the level of reading ability of the subjects during the post-test in silent reading in terms of speed has a mean of 35.5 words per minute, and the mean for post-test in oral reading speed is 39.2 words per minute. In terms post-test comprehension score, silent reading has gained the mean 1.6 and oral reading got the mean of 1.3 and the class proficiency level is 19%.

Based on the results there is an increased of the reading performance of the students after the intervention, as shown in the increased in the post-test results in reading speed and comprehension score in both oral and silent reading.

Consolidated Result of Silent and Oral Reading During Pre-Test and Posttest

Table 3

Formulas	Silent Reading Speed		Silent Reading Comprehension Score		Oral Reading Speed		Oral Reading Comprehension Score	
	Pre test	Post test	Pre Test	Post Test	Pre test	Post Test	Pre Test	Post test
Valid	27	27	27	27	27	27	27	27
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	15.622	35.481	0.111	1.593	10.063	39.237	0.111	1.296
Std. Deviation	2.105	11.628	0.424	1.693	3.096	13.457	0.424	1.540
Minimum	13.800	20.500	0.000	0.000	0.000	14.800	0.000	0.000
Maximum	23.400	63.300	2.000	6.000	15.200	62.300	2.000	6.000

Table 3 presents the consolidated results of oral and silent reading during the pre-test and post-test. There were 27 respondents who participated in both tests, and no one is missing (as represented by 0). Prior to the pre-test, the subjects had not undergone any reading remediation. Remediation commenced only the day after the pre-test to ensure experimental reliability in addressing the statement of the problem.

During the pre-test, the mean of the scores in silent reading speed, measured in words per minute, for the passage with 196 words, was 15.6, and in the post-test the same test yielded a mean of 35.5. This suggests an improvement in reading speed attributable to the plain use of ICT Integration in reading remediation.

On the other hand, the pre-test oral reading speed of struggling readers has the mean of 10.1 words per minute, while in the post-test its mean becomes 39.2 words per minute.

The comprehension score for oral reading during the pre-test had a mean of 0.11, while during the post-test, it increased to 1.6. This indicates an improvement of 1.49 in the subjects' scores during the post-test, suggesting that ICT integration has a positive impact on the subjects' performance. In terms of oral reading comprehension score it got the mean of 0.11, while the post-test comprehension score was 1.3.

Significant Difference in the Pre-test and Post-test Scores in Silent Reading Speed Before and After ICT Integration

Table 4

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Difference in the Pre-test and Post-test in Silent Reading Speed Before and After ICT Integration

Variables	T	Df	P-Value	Remarks
Pre-test Silent Reading Speed				
Post-test Silent Reading Speed	-8.839	26	< .001	Significant

Based on Table 4 there is a significant difference in silent reading speed between pretest and posttest in favor of posttest, which means that ICT integration in reading remediation has improved the reading speed of struggling readers

**Significant Difference in the Pre-test and Post-test in Silent Reading Comprehension Scores
 Before and After ICT Integration**

Table 5

Difference in the Pretest and Posttest in Silent Reading Comprehension Score
 Before and After ICT Integration

Variables	T	Df	P-Value	Remarks
Pre-test Silent Reading Comprehension Score				
Post-test Silent Reading Comprehension Score	-4.481	26	<.001	Significant

Table 5 shows the significant difference of comprehension scores in silent reading speed between pretest and posttest in favor of posttest. The result shows that there is a significant difference in silent reading comprehension scores during the pretest and posttest in favor of the posttest

Significant Difference of Oral Reading Speed Before and After ICT Integration

Table 6

Difference of Oral Reading Speed Before and After ICT Integration

**THE IMPACT OF INTERNET INTEGRATION TO DEVELOP READING ABILITY OF STRUGGLING READERS:
AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY**

Variables	T	Df	P-Value	Remarks
Pre-test Oral Reading Speed				
Post-test Oral Reading Speed	-11.377	26	<.001	Significant

Table 6 shows that there is a significant difference in the pretest and posttest scores in oral reading in terms of speed during the pretest and posttest in favor of the posttest.

Significant Difference of Oral Reading Comprehension Score Before and After ICT Integration 38

Table 7

Difference of Oral Reading Comprehension Score Before and After ICT Integration

Variables	T	Df	P-Value	Remarks
Pre-test Oral Reading Comprehension Score				
Post-test Oral Reading Comprehension Score	-3.986	26	<.001	Significant

Table 7 shows that there is a significant difference in oral reading comprehension score between post-test and pre-test in favor of post-test.

The silent reading speed of the participants after the ICT integration has gained an increase of 19.9 words as depicted in post-test result. It shows that the same integration has improved the silent reading speed of the respondents.

On the other hand, the pre-test result on oral reading speed of the subjects has an increased of 29.1 words per minute, which indicates that the said integration on the reading intervention has a positive impact to the subjects .

Furthermore, the results give clearer data that the pretest silent reading comprehension scores has an increased of 1.49.

Lastly, the pre-test comprehension score in oral reading got an increased of 1.19 from the previous scores after the post-test.

The overall results are aligned with the studies of Mayes et al. (2001) and Solak (2014) about the potential benefits of digital reading in terms of speed and comprehension. While earlier research

indicated mixed findings regarding the efficacy of digital versus paper-based reading, recent studies have suggested that digital reading can indeed lead to faster reading speeds. ⁴⁰

Taking into account these insights, it can be inferred that the observed improvement in reading speed among struggling readers following ICT integration, as indicated in the provided data, can be attributed to several factors.

Firstly, the dynamic and interactive nature of digital texts, coupled with the convenience of internet access, may have enhanced students' engagement and motivation to read. Secondly, the utilization of multimedia elements and interactive features, as demonstrated in Nurhana's study, likely facilitated deeper comprehension and retention of reading materials. Finally, the broader accessibility of digital resources enabled by ICT integration may have provided struggling readers with a more diverse and stimulating reading environment, ultimately contributing to their improved reading speed and comprehension.

Thus the integration of ICT in reading remediation offers a multifaceted approach to enhancing reading skills among struggling readers. By leveraging digital technologies and internet connectivity, educators can create immersive learning experiences that cater to the diverse needs and preferences of students in today's digital age. Moreover, Adalakun et al., (2022) studied the benefits, challenges and prospects of Electronic Learning System using two research processes administered to students and lecturers, and the findings of their study show that information technology will improve performance and lead to greater productivity when standard IT infrastructure is installed.

Hence, all education curricula should be incorporated with appropriate digital technology to meet the present and future challenges of globalization and the knowledge economy.

Thierer (2000) pointed out that the role of technology in teaching and learning is rapidly becoming one of the most important and widely discussed issues in contemporary education policy. Its importance has been recognized by educational institutions worldwide (Watson, 2001). After the treatment of data, results show that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test results in favor of post-test in terms of speed, and comprehension scores in both oral and silent reading.

This means that the integration of the ICT in teaching reading has a positive impact of the reading comprehension and speed either silent or oral reading for struggling readers.

The increased access to digital materials through the internet has transformed the reading habits of students, motivating them to engage more with electronic texts.

Therefore, the findings suggest that ICT integration plays a crucial role in improving the reading proficiency of struggling readers, aligning with the broader goal of leveraging technology to enhance educational outcomes (Pardede, 2012; Nurhana, 2014; Solak, 2014; Sudiran, 2015; UNESCO, 2015).

5. Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Given the significant positive impact of ICT integration on the reading abilities of struggling readers, parents must not only negatively view the use of gadgets but they also encourage to wisely utilize gadgets and access to the internet for their children with utmost supervision. Parents should provide supervised access to digital reading materials and educational resources, fostering a supportive environment that promotes engagement with electronic texts.
2. Parents can collaborate with educators to ensure that the use of technology aligns with their child's individual learning needs and preferences.
3. Struggling readers themselves should embrace the opportunities provided by ICT integration for reading remediation. They should actively engage with digital texts and utilize interactive features to enhance their reading speed and comprehension. Seeking guidance from educators and parents on effective strategies for utilizing technology for reading improvement can further support their progress. By taking advantage of digital resources, struggling readers can develop stronger reading skills and boost their confidence in literacy.
4. Educators play a crucial role in facilitating the effective integration of ICT into reading remediation for struggling readers. Teachers should receive professional development training on utilizing digital technologies for literacy instruction, including strategies for incorporating multimedia elements and interactive features into lessons.
5. Teachers must collaborate with parents and leveraging technology-enhanced learning platforms can create a supportive learning environment that maximizes the benefits of ICT integration for reading improvement.
6. The Department of Education (DepEd) should prioritize the integration of ICT into reading remediation programs for struggling readers at the policy level. DepEd officials should allocate resources for the development of digital literacy initiatives and provide support for schools to access educational technology tools and resources.
7. The Department of Education (DepEd) should establish guidelines and standards for the effective use of ICT in literacy instruction, ensuring that educators receive adequate training and support. By fostering a culture of technological innovation in education, DepEd can enhance reading outcomes for struggling readers and promote inclusivity in learning.

6. Conclusion

After exclusively using ICT for remediation for struggling readers the post-test results indicate a significant difference in reading speed and comprehension scores during the pre-test and post-test, favoring the post-test outcomes. This suggests that the implementation of ICT has positively impacted the reading abilities of struggling readers.. The observed results clearly indicate a significant difference in favor of the posttest, underscoring the positive impact of ICT integration on reading abilities of struggling readers.

7. Acknowledgements

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8. About the Author(s)

Neneth R. Sargento is currently a public elementary teacher. Her interests are painting, writing articles, reading books about Philippine Law and reading novels too. She is also currently taking master's degree at Assumption College of Nabunturan, Davao de Oro Philippines, wherein her thesis adviser, **Elizabeth D. Dioso (EdD)**, a graduate school faculty member of Assumption College of Nabunturan, Nabunturan, Davao de Oro, Philippines was her co-author of the said study.

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B. ELEMENTS

a. Figures and Tables

The figures and tables should have a numbered explanatory label posted below the graphic element. Each figure and table should have a descriptive caption that describes and defines all the abbreviations included. If the element contains data from external sources, an explanatory citation should be included. Photographic images can be submitted if they are saved in JPEG format at a resolution of 300 dpi. The tables are required to have, if appropriate or possible, the width and the height of the size of an entire page avoiding the splitting on more pages.

b. Formulas and Equations

The formulas and equation could be inserted as objects if created with another external program (Wolfram Mathematica, Matlab, etc) or by using Microsoft Equation Editor included on the last editions of Microsoft Office.

c. Lists

Any kind of list can be part of the article. Numbers, letters, roman numbers, bullets, etc. can be used as their components.

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d. Supplementary Files

**CONSOLIDATED RESULT FOR ORAL READING PRE-TEST AND
 POST-TEST**

RESPONDENTS	PRE-TEST			POST-TEST		
	SCORE	READING TIME IN SECONDS	SPEED	SCORE	READING TIME IN SECONDS	SPEED
1	0	480	9.5	3	116	39.3
2	0	510	8.94118	2	94.2	48.4
3	0	480	9.5	0	307.2	14.84
4	0	480	9.5	0	111	41.08
5	0	480	9.5	0	206	22.14
6	0	510	8.94118	0	204	22.35
7	0	540	8.44444	0	75	60.8
8	0	450	10.1333	1	211	21.61
9	2	300	15.2	3	148.8	30.65
10	0	300	15.2	1	74	61.63
11	0	516	8.83721	3	112	40.71
12	0	510	8.94118	2	126	36.19
13	0	480	9.5	0	79.8	57.14
14	1	522	8.73563	0	114	40
15	0	480	9.5	1	83.4	54.68
16	0	510	8.94118	1	222	20.54
17	0	498	9.15663	0	113	40.35
18	0	492	9.26829	6	73.2	62.3
19	0	486	9.38272	0	92.4	49.35
20	0	450	10.1333	0	150	30.4
21	0	450	10.1333	0	126	36.19
22	0	300	15.2	0	126	36.19
23	0	300	15.2	2	108	42.22
24	0	300	15.2	1	131.4	34.7
25	0	480	9.5	3	87.6	52.05
26	0	480	9.5	3	114	40
27	0	390	0	3	194	23.5

Number of Words for Oral Reading Passage: 76

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{Phil-IRRI} \\
 \text{Formula}
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \text{Speed}
 \quad
 =
 \quad
 \frac{\text{Number of Words in the Passage}}{\text{Times in Seconds}}
 \quad
 \times
 \quad
 60$$

C. LIMITATIONS

There is absolutely **no limit** and **no extra charges** on:

how many pages are allowed for a research paper. It depends on many factors, the researcher should decide that. A 5-25 pages research article it is only a recommendation, not a limit.

how many authors a research paper may have. Collaboration is the key.

how many graphic elements, figures, pictures, photos, tables, appendixes a research paper may contain. We are strongly encouraging our authors on providing any possible method designated to ensure better and faster information exchange.

D. MANUSCRIPT FILE FORMAT

A Microsoft Word, any version (2003, 2010), file or any other document editor is recommended. External files as PowerPoint presentation, image files (*.jpg, *.bmp, *.png), Excel tables, AutoCAD files, can be included.

E. LANGUAGES ACCEPTED

Article written on English, Spanish, Portuguese, Italian and French are accepted. They can contain abstracts\titles on English too. Articles written in two columns (English + another language) are accepted.

Neneth R. Sargento, Elizabeth D. Dioso
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AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY
